

Collaborative Working

What would you like to work on?

Document experiments, research and procedures

Organize group activities and lab resources

Write publications or documentations

Organize and document literature

Electronic lab notebook

- At the Uni ... **eLabFTW**
- ✓ Versioning
- ✓ Formula editor
- ✓ Manage equipment
- ✓ Tagging
- ✓ Data stored on campus

Wiki

- At the Uni ... **XWiki**
- ✓ Versioning
- ✓ Tagging
- ✓ MS-Office compatibel
- ✓ Data stored on campus

Online Texteditor

- At the Uni ... **SciFlow**
- ✓ Word inspired
- ✓ Publication templates
- ✓ Zotero compatible
- ✓ Data stored in Germany

Reference management

- At the Uni ... **Citavi**
- ✓ Integration in MS Word
- ✓ Several citation styles available
- ✓ Add sources automatically from your web browser

- At the Uni ... **ILIAS**
- ✓ Versioning
- ✓ Rating and commenting
- ✓ Collaborative writing with Etherpad
- ✓ Data stored on campus

- In Sciebo ... **Overleaf**
- ✓ LaTeX Editor
- ✓ Publication templates
- ✓ Commenting
- ✓ Data stored in Germany

- In Sciebo ... **OnlyOffice**
- ✓ Office inspired
- ✓ Data stored in Germany

Need more details?
Visit us on ILIAS

- Browser access
- Windows application
- Linux application
- Mac application
- Additional costs
- Open Source Software